

BIOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION IN LYCOPERSICON ESCULENTUM GROWTH UNDER TEXTILE EFFLUENT STRESS AND SILICON TREATMENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17164778>

Keywords

waste water stress, extile effluent stress, chlorophyll and carotenoids

Article History

Received: 21 June 2025

Accepted: 31 August 2025

Published: 20 September 2025

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Abstract

Textile industry is one impressive industry which provides not only the employment but also imparts hazardous impacts on plants and humans. Tomatoes also contain chlorogenic acid, which helps in lowering the blood pressure. Tomatoes can cause oral allergic syndrome, which is basically caused by allergic reactions. Silicon is one of the elements which are not considered as essential elements but it has been observed that it minimizes several abiotic and biotic stresses and its beneficial for development and growth of several plants, especially of cyperaceous and gramineous plants. In present research, pot experiment was designed to analyze the role of silicon in the growth regulation of *Lycopersicon esculentum* and its therapeutic role under textile waste water stress. Textile effluent stress (Control, 10% and 20%) reduced growth considerably and application of Si (2 μ mol/L) enhanced growth and also mitigated the detrimental effects of textile effluent. Tomato plants accumulated heavy metals at large extent under stress while Si successfully alleviated the heavy metals concentration in tomato plant.

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is a fruit but according to its botanical definition it is considered as vegetable. Tomatoes are found in different colors like green, yellow, purple and orange, but commonly they get red color when matured. About 95% of tomato's content is water while remaining 5% is source of essential mineral like potassium, Vitamin-K, Vitamin-C and folate (Komal *et al.*, 2014). Tomatoes are source of naringenin, that helps in reducing inflammation. Tomatoes contain an antioxidant lycopene, that reduces the chances of cancer and heart diseases. Tomatoes are source of beta carotene which get converted into Vitamin-A when ingested in our body. Tomatoes also contain

chlorogenic acid, which helps in lowering the blood pressure. Tomatoes can cause oral allergic syndrome, which is basically caused by allergic reactions. These are the reactions which are caused by attack of immune system on fruit or vegetable proteins, which are the same as pollen proteins (Watanabe *et al.*, 2006).

Silicon is one of the elements which are not considered as essential elements but it has been observed that it minimizes several abiotic and biotic stresses and its beneficial for development and growth of several plants, especially of cyperaceous and gramineous plants (Mengel *et al.*, 2011). Silicon

increases plant's ability to resist against pests, fungi as well as to drought conditions. Silicon also alleviates the severe effects of heavy metals, aluminum. Both the silicon deposited in plant tissues and the soluble silicon are beneficial. Silicon is deposited in plant tissue act as barrier to increase the strength and rigidity of plant tissues. Si can alleviate various stresses including biotic, abiotic and heavy metal stresses, and it can also stimulate plant growth (Adrees *et al.*, 2015). While the demand of water to irrigate is increasing day by day to meet the needs of ever increasing population. To meet the needs of irrigation water demand, we must have to move to non-conventional resources, within in certain limits. Amongst others, industrial waste water is most important and nutrient resource. The industrial waste water could be utilized by two ways one is by water treatment methods and second one is by the use of alleviators along with untreated waste water to alleviate toxic effects of heavy metals. This study is undertaken to determine the role of externally used Si as an alleviator in alleviating waste water induced oxidative stress and translocation in tomato plant (Adrees *et al.*, 2015).

This research has following objectives to investigate the impact of textile effluent on growth, of plant and effect of silicon as an alleviator of textile water stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was accomplished in Layyah, in area hired for research point. A Green House was set up there to protect tomato plants from bad weather conditions. The necessary details of project listed below:

Collection of materials

Determinate variety of the tomato named as dwarf money maker seeds were obtained from the market and used for experiment. 25 Plastic pots purchased from local market to grow the plants. Sand, clay and silt were obtained from Layyah, Layyah miner and the fields of the Housing Colony, Layyah respectively.

Experimental plan

Seeds pretreated with the distilled water prior the sowing. Such seeds were sown in the pots during the first week of December. Pots were kept in plastic tunnel. A complete randomized design (CRD) method was opted to carry out this experiment.

Assessment of morphological parameters

Tomato leaves, roots and shoot were removed carefully and washed through distilled water. Length of leaves was measured. The fresh weights of roots, shoots and leaves were measured by using electrical balance in grams.

Statistical analysis

All experiments were conducted in the 6 replicates and data obtained is presented as the mean \pm standard deviation ($M \pm SD$). Furthermore, the data is also being analyzed using computer based statistical package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Root length

Roots are important part of plants performing vital function in plants growth by affecting on final growth and yield. Root length is affected by physical, biological and chemical properties. The result presented in fig 1 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the root length under textile waste water was small than control plant groups.

Figure 1: Effect of Si treatment on the root length (cm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress.

Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$)

Shoot length

Shoots are imperative element of plant performing vital functions in plants growth by affecting on final

growth and yield. Shoot length is affected by physical and chemical properties. The result presented in fig 2 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the shoot length under textile waste water was small than control plant groups.

Fig 2: Effect of Si treatment on the shoot length (cm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Fresh root mass

Fresh root mass or dry root mass denotes the extent of growth and development of plants which is affected by physical and chemical properties. The

result presented in fig 3 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application.

Figure 3: Effect of Si treatment on the fresh root mass (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are M ± S.D (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA (P<0.05).

Fresh shoot mass

Plant growth is considered in terms of fresh shoot mass, greater the shoot mass greater will be the plant growth but environmental and biophysical properties are affected on fresh shoot mass. The result presented in fig 4 shows comparison between control group with

textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the fresh shoot mass under textile waste water was small than control plant groups.

Figure 4: Effect of Si treatment on the fresh shoot mass (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Dry root mass

Dry root mass is important parameter which determines the extent of root growth in plant but environmental and biophysical properties affects on dry root mass. The result presented in fig 5 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also

shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the dry root mass under textile waste water was small than control plant groups. It was noticed that shortening of the dry root mass of the control group as compared to silicon treated control plant group.

Figure 5: Effect of Si treatment on the dry root mass (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$)

Dry shoot mass

Dry shoot mass is a central parameter which determines the extent of shoot growth and development in plants but biological, environmental and biophysical properties affect on dry shoot mass. The result presented in fig 6 shows comparison

between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the dry shoot mass under textile waste water was small than control plant groups.

Figure 6: Effect of Si treatment on the dry shoot mass (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Fresh weight of leaves

Fresh weight of leaves is a major plant parameter which determines the extent of leaves growth and development in plants but biological, environmental and biophysical properties affects on fresh weight of leaves. The result presented in fig 7 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress

(10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the fresh weight of leaves under textile waste water was small than control plant groups. It was noticed that shortening of the fresh weight of leaves of the control group as compared to silicon treated control plant group.

Figure 7: Effect of Si treatment on the fresh weight of leaves (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are M ± S.D (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA (P<0.05)

Dry weight of leaves

Dry weight of leaves is important plant parameter that determines extent of leaves growth and development in plants but biological, environmental and biophysical properties affects on dry weight of leaves.

The result presented in fig 8 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application.

Figure 8: Effect of Si treatment on the dry weight of leaves (gm) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Leaf area

The most important character of plant growth is leaf area of plant which affects from various stresses. The result presented in fig 9 shows comparison between control group with textile waste water stress (10% and 20%) tomato plant and also shows impact of Si by foliar application. Our results reveal that the leaf area under textile waste water was small than control plant

groups. It was noticed that shortening of the leaf area of the control group as compared to silicon treated control plant group. Silicon applied tomato plants showed positive impacts on leaf area under textile waste water. One way ANOVA analysis of data shows significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in leaf area of plant after Si treatment.

Figure 9: Effect of Si treatment on the leaf area (cm²) of tomato under the control and textile water stress. Values are $M \pm S.D$ (N=3). Data analyzed by using One-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

The prescribed result is according with work of Marwari & Khan, (2012), who investigated the response of textile waste water stress (0%, 20% and 30%) on tomato plants. The plants show significant growth inhibition including root length and others morphological parameters than control group plants. This might be due to textile waste water contain rich amount of heavy metals which inhibit the transportation of essential nutrients necessary for plant growth. Similarly, our prescribed study also according with observation of Sattar *et al* (2016) who investigated that Si treated plants reveal significantly boost root length than the control groups by ameliorating stress. This might be possible due to Si mitigates the textile water stress by formation of chelates with heavy metal in the roots and allows uptake of the essential nutrients responsible in amplify of the root length. Thus, reducing uptake of toxic heavy metals form apoplasmic barriers and maturing the root tissues which result in boost of root length (Adrees *et al.*, 2015).

The prescribed result is according with work of Vega, (2019), who determined that textile waste water stress (0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%) reduced the fresh shoot mass and biomass of wheat plant. This reduced fresh shoot mass is might be due to bioaccumulation of heavy metals in shoots which stunts the transportation of major nutrients to leaves and other parts which required for growth and development. The prescribed results are according with study of Mercedes *et al.*, (2006) who noticed the mitigation effect of silicon under heavy metals stress in tomato and he also observed the significant increase in fresh shoot weight than stressed group. This is due to Si improves fresh shoot weight and growth by enhancing the plasmomembrane stability and reducing damages of cell membrane.

The prescribed result is according with work of Muhammad *et al.*, (2015), who determined that industrial waste water stress (0%, 20%, 30% , 40% and 50%) reduced the chlorophyll 'b' in *Cicer arietum*. This reduced chlorophyll 'b' is might be due to bioaccumulation of heavy metals in leaves which reduce growth and reduced photosynthesis rate. Heavy metals react with functional group of chlorophylls which reduce the mitosis resulting low production of chlorophylls. The prescribed results are

according with study of Sarkar *et al.*, (2020), who observed the response of Si on wheat cultivar which enhanced the chlorophyll 'b' contents under stressed conditions. This might be due to Si increases plant tolerance against the stressed conditions by improving plant growth. Silicon enhances metabolism and photosynthetic PSII activities in the cells which deliberately increases photosynthesis.

Our results are supported by the work of Islam *et al.* (2017) for *Cassia italica* who reported that phenolics levels generally rise as rise with stress level of heavy metals. Our results are also supported by Ahmad & Haddad, (2011) who investigated that Si enhances the phenolics profile in sunflower. This might be possible due to fact that plants enhance the phenolics profile to cope the oxidative stress to some extent while Si favours the elevation of phenolics and antioxidant enzymes activity to alleviate heavy metals stress.

Conclusion

Textile effluent stress is foremost disaster for fertility and productivity of agricultural systems. In the present research, experiments were conducted to mitigate the textile effluent stress by foliar treatment of Si on tomato plants. Textile effluent stress reduced plant morphological and photosynthetic pigments while Si application improved these parameters. Antioxidant enzymes (SOD, POX, CAT) generally enhanced under textile effluent stress whereas Si further improved the enzymatic and non enzymatic antioxidants. Tomato plants accumulated heavy metals at large extent under stress while Si successfully alleviated the heavy metals concentration in tomato plant. From above findings we can conclude that textile waste water can be used for irrigation purpose after proper treatment like Si application.

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